

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

Vafa Isgandarova

PhD, Baku State University

Vafa1.aslan@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4167-7531>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14956661>

DATA LITERACY: THE ISSUE OF DATA USAGE IN AZERBAIJANI SOCIAL MEDIA

Abstract:

After the industrial revolutions, we see the increasing role of data in various fields. Depending on the ability to collect, analyze, correctly process and use them in the areas of application, the development prospects are also increasing. These skills, which are also of great importance in the field of data journalism, allow you to create a good media product. The article discusses the importance of big data, data literacy and the essence of how data is used in Azerbaijani social media. Data from the websites Azertac, Modern.az, Report.az, Axar.az and Yeni Çağ.info, and their visualization were monitored and included in the analysis in here.

Keywords: data, literacy, processing, social media, convergence

Introduction. In modern times, data products, which are an integral part of investigative journalism, are considered to be deeper and more useful sources than traditional media materials. In order to prepare data journalism materials, it is important to first acquire data literacy skills. Data-literate journalists can review large data sets, identifying trends and additional indicators that are not immediately visible in traditional sources. Many investigative stories are based on data analysis to highlight and solve socio-political and social problems that are necessary for society. That is, being able to interpret complex data sets more accurately is a key skill for investigative journalists.

Data-driven stories can increase transparency by providing evidence-based reporting. By using data, journalists can support their claims and at the same time make their work more reliable. Data products have interactive content. Thus, data literacy helps journalists create engaging, interactive stories, such as visualizations and data-driven news programs that engage the audience in new ways. This requires fact-checking first. Because in the age of disinformation, it is very important for journalists and the audience to verify information and distinguish between reliable and unreliable sources. Data literacy also requires the instillation of critical thinking. “Jessica Pucci, a colleague at the University of Arizona, unequivocally recommends a critical approach to numbers. She says that data literacy is the critical skill of the 21st century, and these skills will change the world for the better. Data is not always understandable. People need more accessible data, otherwise they will refuse it” [1, p. 102]

Miro Kazakoff, a professor at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, emphasizes that in a data-rich world, it is precisely companies with high data literacy that will occupy a leading position. In general, data literacy has always been considered an important competence in companies. It is simply that in modern times, data illiteracy is more clearly felt or causes more damage to companies than in previous years

[<https://tedroid.com/meqale/data-savadligi-artirila-biler.html>]

With the formation of the information society, the collection, processing and analysis of data is becoming increasingly important. Data literacy acts as a key factor in the effective decision-making processes of individuals, organizations and societies in the modern world. Enakrire notes that the ability to work with data is not limited to technical knowledge alone, but also includes complex processes such as reading, interpreting and using data correctly. In this context, the data literacy cycle is a systematic approach that covers the sequential stages from data acquisition to its analysis, interpretation and decision-making based on the results

[<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/lhtn-01-2020-0005/full/html>].

Conceptualization. An object, variable, or piece of information that has the ability to be perceived for data collection, which can be stored and identified. It mainly comes in two forms: structured and unstructured. Structured data are essentially answers to questions posed by the data collector, generally, it is possible to obtain and systematize this type of statistical data, they have a strict hierarchy that is not easily manipulated. For example, survey responses organized in a tabular format, people's years of education, income, birth and death statistics, etc.

Unstructured data is actually somewhat different from the intended purpose when it was collected, is not easily amenable to automated analysis, and is often used. For example, tweets, photos, videos, and similar data do not need to adhere to the hierarchical identification method. Both types of data play a major role in the data ecosystem, strongly influencing society.

Literacy is the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, and calculate information using printed and written materials related to various contexts. Literacy enables individuals to achieve their goals, develop their knowledge and

potential, and participate fully in their communities and the wider society.

In an era of widespread new media and technology, various types of literacy such as digital, media, and information have emerged. Data literacy is defined and conceptualized as the willingness and ability to participate constructively in society through data. Data literacy enables people globally to use different types of data to improve their lives and strengthen their communities. Both journalists who produce data content and the readers and listeners who access it must be data literate.

As we have noted, researchers identify the following stages of data product development:

The first stage, data reading, involves understanding the structure, sources, and how the data represents reality. The next step, data production, involves the processes of collecting, cleaning, and managing data. This stage requires the application of the necessary methods to obtain accurate and reliable information. The third stage is data analysis, which involves sorting, comparing, and processing data using certain methods to draw conclusions. At this stage, statistical methods and data visualization techniques are applied, which create conditions for a deeper understanding of the information. The final stage is to discuss the data. This refers to the use of data to support a narrative or message aimed at a specific audience. Using data at this stage, it becomes possible to explain social, economic, and technological issues more clearly [https://www.dataversity.net/data-literacy-trends-in-2023-formalizing-programs/].

Based on the materials from 2024-2025 that we have included in the monitoring, Azertag, the first and largest news agency in Azerbaijan, presents visualizations of data related to country events in a separate section under the heading "Infographics". However, their analysis or explanatory content for the audience is not provided [https://azertag.az/infografika]. This makes it difficult for people to perceive information more easily.

Modern az website provides infographic visuals under various news headlines. However, these news items are mainly about events occurring in other countries. At the same time, the visuals of these articles consist of statistical data prepared by media organizations of the same countries [https://modern.az/news/397886/].

The Internet media site Report.az, which is part of the country's largest media holding, "Global Media Group", does not present any visualization of infographics in its data products, the main essence of which is related to the economy, but only includes various statistical figures and mathematical calculations within the text. A large segment of the population has difficulty reading, analyzing, comparing and using this data.

The number of data products on the Axar az website, which is part of the same media group, is a minority. Only the article "Journalism Trends in Our Media: Problems and Solutions" provides data visual presentations [https://axar.az/news/toplum/908383.html]. In other

products, which are mainly about war, only maps from foreign sources are used.

Yeniçağ information portal also gave little space to infographic data visuals among the materials it published in 2024-2025. Only in relation to a number of global problems occurring in foreign countries, infographics that were not produced by the company were used [https://yenicag.az/hansi-olkenin-ne-qeder-nuve-baslighi-var-bu-uc-olke-birlikde-rusiyadan-geri-qalir-foto/].

Although convergent products consisting of hyperlinks, photos, video reports, and texts are widely published on the media sites we researched, data products are few in number. Those that are found are mostly those taken from external sources or only infographic materials, as well as texts consisting only of statistical content. This makes the local audience lazy in terms of data literacy. For this reason, it is important to bring a large number of data products to the attention of readers.

Conclusion. In the modern information society, individuals and organizations are forced to manage, analyze and purposefully use large volumes of data. In this context, data literacy is a complex skill area that encompasses the process of obtaining, processing, interpreting data and drawing meaningful conclusions through analytical approaches [https://www.dataversity.net/data-literacy-trends-in-2023-formalizing-programs/]. Analysis of the literature on the topic and monitoring of social media entities show that the data literacy of both producers and consumers of social media products in Azerbaijan is unsatisfactory. This makes the local audience lazy in terms of data literacy. For this reason, it is important to bring a large number of data products to the attention of readers. The most important issue is developing people's critical thinking skills from a very young age. Because, regardless of age, race, gender, standard of living, or worldview, the entire population is an active user of media.

However, against the background of the aforementioned developments, the demand for more systematic and corporate approaches in the field of data literacy is growing every day. According to forecasts of research institutions, by 2026, approximately 40% of large enterprises will implement formal data literacy programs. This trend will make the contribution of data to strategic decision-making, risk management, and innovation more sustainable at the corporate level [https://www.dataversity.net/data-literacy-trends-in-2023-formalizing-programs/]. Therefore, there is a benefit in developing data literacy in all fields, especially in the media sphere.

References

1. Almaz Mahmud. Media savadlılığı jurnalistlər üçün. Bakı 2022. 160 səhifə
2. https://tedroid.com/meqale/data-savadliligi-artirila-biler.html
3. https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/lhtn-01-2020-0005/full/html
4. https://www.dataversity.net/data-literacy-trends-in-2023-formalizing-programs/

5. <https://azertag.az/infografika>
6. <https://modern.az/news/397886/>
7. <https://axar.az/news/toplum/908383.html>
8. <https://yenicag.az/hansi-olkenin-ne-qeder-nuve-basligi-var-bu-uc-olke-birlikde-rusiyadan-geri-qalir-foto/>
9. <https://www.dataversity.net/data-literacy-trends-in-2023-formalizing-programs>